
LMM-ASSISTED SUBCLASS-AWARE ZERO-SHOT INDUSTRIAL DEFECT DETECTION ^{*†}

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ABSTRACT

Industrial defect detection is a crucial task in manufacturing associated with many critical applications. The scarcity of labeled defective data renders it a particularly challenging task, with many recent approaches adopting the Zero-Shot Anomaly Detection (ZSAD) paradigm to address it. The vast majority of them employ CLIP-based models. In this paper, we propose a novel *LMM-assisted Subclass-Aware* method for improving the performance of a downstream CLIP-based model for ZSAD. Specifically, we first prompt an LMM specialized for anomaly detection, in order to extract *defect-type* descriptions for the defective images of an auxiliary dataset. Then, we extract their corresponding CLIP text embeddings and compute the k defect-type center embeddings. Subsequently, during the downstream model's training, we introduce an additional subclass objective that maximizes the cosine similarity between the defective image embeddings and their most similar, in terms of cosine similarity, center embedding of LMM-generated defect types. In this way, images with the same defect type are forced to be close even if their underlying object category is different. That is, the proposed objective promotes cross-category defect-type discrimination, improving in this way the defect discrimination. We apply the proposed method on a state-of-the-art model for ZSAD, significantly improving its performance.

Keywords industrial defect detection · LMMs · subclass-aware · CLIP.

1 Introduction

Industrial defect detection refers to the task of identifying defective or anomalous samples among normal industrial products and localizing the defect regions within the images [1, 2, 3]. Defect detection is associated with many critical applications, such as automated visual industrial inspection and quality control management, rendering it as a task of utmost importance in manufacturing [4]. It falls under the broader task of anomaly detection which has been extensively studied over the past years. A major challenge in the anomaly detection task is the scarcity of labeled anomalous data, leading to the traditional unsupervised paradigm that aims at modeling the normal data distribution using only normal samples [5, 6]. However, acquiring such data in real-world scenarios may be extremely challenging (e.g., detecting defects in a production line for new products), and hence the Zero-Shot Anomaly Detection (ZSAD) paradigm is widely used in the current research. ZSAD, instead of using target-domain training data, uses auxiliary data for training, remedying in this way the challenges linked with the data availability. Following the exceptional zero-shot performance of the CLIP vision-language model [7], the vast majority of recent ZSAD methods utilize CLIP-based variants [8, 9, 10].

Over the past few years, Large Language Models (LLMs) [11] and Large Multimodal Models (LMMs) (also known as multimodal LLMs) [12], have been utilized for addressing a plethora of downstream vision recognition tasks,

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accomplishing exceptional performance [13, 14]. Apart from the general-purpose, LMMs specialized for ZSAD tasks have recently been proposed, including models such as AnomalyGPT [15] and Anomaly-OV [16].

In this paper, we propose a novel method to address the industrial defect detection task pursuing the ZSAD direction, by exploiting the emerging capabilities of LMMs. More expressly, we propose an *LMM-assisted Subclass-Aware* method for improving the performance of a state-of-the-art CLIP-based model for ZSAD. To do so, we first prompt an LMM specialized for ZSAD to obtain defect-type descriptions for the defective images of the auxiliary dataset. Then, we aim to introduce this knowledge to improve the detection performance of the downstream CLIP-based model. To this end, once the defect-type descriptions are generated, we use the frozen text encoder of the utilized CLIP-based model in order to extract the corresponding defect-type text embeddings. Subsequently, we apply k -means clustering to the aforementioned defective text embeddings in order to obtain the k defect-type center embeddings. Next, during the training of the downstream model for ZSAD, we introduce an additional subclass objective that forces the image embeddings of the defective images to come closer to their most similar text center embedding in the shared image-text embeddings space, promoting the formation of defect-type subclasses inside the defect class. Specifically, the additional objective maximizes the cosine similarity between the image embeddings of the defective images and their most similar, in terms of cosine similarity, center embedding of LMM-generated defect types. In this way, images with the same defect type are encouraged to be close even if their underlying object category is different. That is, while CLIP embeddings naturally cluster images by objects, the proposed objective promotes cross-category defect-type discrimination, improving in this way the defect discrimination, as it is experimentally validated. We finally note that in this paper we utilized the AF-CLIP model [10] as the downstream CLIP-based model for ZSAD, since, to the best of our knowledge, it represents the current state-of-the-art, however it should be emphasized that the proposed subclass-aware method is not tied to any specific CLIP-based architecture.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly discusses previous CLIP-based approaches for ZSAD. Section 3 presents in detail the proposed LMM-assisted subclass-aware method for ZSAD. Subsequently, Section 4 presents the conducted experiments for validating the effectiveness of the proposed method, while Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of this work.

2 Related Work

In this section we briefly discuss previous CLIP-based methods for ZSAD. WinCLIP [8] is the first CLIP-based work to address the industrial defect detection task within the ZSAD paradigm. The WinCLIP model, focusing on language, first proposes a prompt ensemble strategy in order to better describe normal and anomalous states. Furthermore, it proposes to extract and aggregate multi-scale spatial features aligned with language in order to address the pixel-level classification. Next, following the same prompt design strategy, APRIL-GAN [17] proposes to use a linear adapter for projecting fine-grained patch features into a joint embedding space.

Subsequently, AnomalyCLIP [18] proposes to learn object-agnostic text prompts capturing generic normality and abnormality in images, in order to enhance CLIP’s understanding of the visual normality-abnormality beyond class semantics. In addition, AnomalyCLIP proposes both image-level and pixel-level loss functions, in order to learn generic normality and abnormality both globally and locally. In a similar direction, AdaCLIP [19] proposes to learn hybrid prompts, i.e., static prompts and dynamic prompts. The former ones are shared across all images, while the latter ones are produced for each test image. Next, SimCLIP [20] proposes a multi-hierarchy vision adapter and a learnable task-specific prompt embedding in order to improve the misalignment between language and vision features. Bayes-PFL [21] proposes to model the prompt space as a learnable probability distribution, utilizing a prompt flow module that learns both image-specific and image-agnostic distributions which are jointly utilized as regularizers to the text prompt space. Also, a residual cross-model attention module is designed for better aligning the dynamic text embeddings with image embeddings.

Furthermore, AA-CLIP [9] proposes a two-stage method aiming to embed anomaly-aware information into CLIP. In the first stage, the text encoder is adapted with frozen visual encoder, producing for each class the so-called anchors for anomaly-aware semantics. In the second stage, patch-level visual features are aligned with the adapted text anchors. In both stages, simple residual adapters are introduced, keeping the original CLIP parameters frozen, in order to preserve the CLIP’s pretrained knowledge and achieve the adaptation to the task. Finally, AF-CLIP [10], which is used in this paper, also introduces a lightweight attention adapter at the output of the layers of CLIP’s visual encoder. Keeping the encoder’s parameters frozen, the adapter is finetuned, adapting CLIP to focus on local anomalies. In addition, a spatial aggregation step is performed before the feature adaptation by multi-scale sliding windows, while a patch alignment loss is also utilized in order to preserve the discrimination between the visual features of normal and abnormal patches. Apart from the visual adaptations, a prompt learning technique is also applied. Notably, the proposed method

Figure 1: Proposed method: In the first stage we prompt the LMM with the defective images along with the depicted text query in order to extract defect-type descriptions for the defective images. In the second stage, we first compute their corresponding CLIP text embeddings, and apply k -means clustering in order to obtain the k center embeddings of defect types. Then, we train the downstream AF-CLIP with an additional subclass objective in the shared image-text space, that maximizes the cosine similarity between each defective image embedding and its most similar center embedding of the LMM-generated defect-type descriptions. The additional subclass objective is applied both for the global and patch defective image embeddings. Note that the figure illustrates only the additional proposed objective, and not the original’s AF-CLIP training objectives.

is orthogonal to the aforementioned CLIP-based approaches for ZSAD. It can be applied to the CLIP’s image-text embedding space for enhancing the defect discrimination, exploiting LMM-generated knowledge.

3 Proposed Method

In this work, we propose an *LMM-assisted Subclass-Aware* method for improving the performance of a CLIP-based model for ZSAD. Specifically, as illustrated in Fig. 1, we first use the Anomaly-OV model to extract defect-type descriptions for the defective images of the auxiliary dataset, and then introduce an additional subclass objective to improve the performance of the AF-CLIP model. In the following, we briefly present the Anomaly-OV and AF-CLIP models, and subsequently, we present the proposed method.

3.1 Preliminaries

3.1.1 Anomaly-OV

Despite the fact that LMMs have exhibited impressive general visual reasoning capabilities, existing general-purpose models struggle to detect and describe subtle anomalies. To this end, Anomaly-OV is proposed for ZSAD and fine-grained anomaly reasoning, by extending LLaVA-OneVision [22] with a dedicated anomaly expert, which operates on multi-level ViT features. Particularly, these features are obtained from four intermediate transformer layers, processed through lightweight adapters, and fed into a look-twice feature matching mechanism. Anomaly-OV is trained through a two-phase process: first, its anomaly expert is optimized with image-level anomaly labels from the large-scale Anomaly-Instruct-125k dataset, and then, the expert is frozen and the language model is instruction-tuned using a mixture of Anomaly-Instruct-125k and roughly 350k general vision-language samples from LLaVA-OneVision.

3.1.2 AF-CLIP

AF-CLIP aims at improving the CLIP’s defect detection performance by introducing a lightweight adaptor module based on trainable attention mechanisms, as well as a spatial aggregation module before the adaptor. More specifically, considering the CLIP’s image encoder $f_I(\cdot)$, text encoder $f_T(\cdot)$, and projection head $f_P(\cdot)$, first the image encoder is

partitioned into four hierarchical blocks, $\mathcal{L} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, and the visual features are extracted from each block. That is, for an input image x : $a^\ell = [a_{CLS}^\ell, a_1^\ell, \dots, a_N^\ell] = f_I^\ell(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times d}$, where $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, while a_{CLS}^ℓ and $\{a_i^\ell\}_{i=1}^N$ are the global and patch tokens respectively. Then, the patch features a^ℓ are reshaped into spatial feature maps b^ℓ and spatial aggregation is performed under different window sizes $r \in \mathcal{R} = 1, 3, 5$, resulting in the aggregated features $\tilde{b}^{\ell r} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$, which, combined with the class token, form the multi-scale visual features: $c^{\ell r} = [a_{CLS}^\ell; \tilde{b}^{\ell r}]$. Then, the spatial-aware features $c^{\ell r}$ are fed to the adaptor $\mathcal{H}_a(\cdot)$ to obtain the anomaly-relevant visual features $\tilde{c}^{\ell r} = \mathcal{H}_a(c^{\ell r})$, which are then projected into the joint image-text space using the projection head f_P of the original CLIP: $z^{\ell r} = f_P(\tilde{c}^{\ell r}) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times t}$, where t is the dimension of the final visual features. Regarding the text features, a prompt learning approach is developed, using fixed state-descriptive suffixes (i.e., with/without defect) and learnable parameters, i.e., P_a and P_n respectively. These prompts are propagated to the text encoder f_T to obtain the anomalous and normal representations, i.e., $t_a = f_T(P_a)$ and $t_n = f_T(P_n)$. Finally, the anomaly scores are computed by aligning, using cosine similarity, the visual features and text embedding prompts. The whole score, measuring the overall similarity between the i -th visual feature and the embeddings of normal/anomalous text prompts, is computed by summing the score over all blocks ℓ and scales r , and then the probability for a visual token being anomalous is denoted as p_i , $i \in \{CLS, 1, \dots, N\}$; p_{CLS} is used for the classification loss, while p_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ for the segmentation loss. Specifically, the AF-CLIP model, with frozen the pretrained CLIP, trains the parameters of the adaptor and learnable prompt embeddings, using three loss components: the image-level classification loss, $\mathcal{L}_{cls} = Focal_Loss(p_{CLS}, y)$ where y denotes the image-level class label, the pixel-level segmentation loss, $\mathcal{L}_{seg} = Focal_Loss(\tilde{P}, \tilde{M}) + L_1(\tilde{P}, \tilde{M})$, where $\tilde{P} = Reshape([p_1, \dots, p_N])$ and \tilde{M} the resized pixel-level labels, and the patch alignment loss, \mathcal{L}_{pal} , applied on patch level features $z_i^{\ell r}$ and averaged over all layers and scales to improve their discrimination ability.

3.1.3 LMM-assisted Subclass-Aware Industrial Defect Detection

The proposed method consists of two stages. We consider the auxiliary dataset $\{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{M}\}$ that contains normal and anomalous images, $x \in \mathcal{X}$, along with the image-level labels $y \in \mathcal{Y}$, and pixel-level labels $M \in \mathcal{M}$. In the first stage, we use Anomaly-OV to obtain defect-type descriptions for the defective images of the auxiliary dataset, $\{x|y=1\}$. To do so, we prompt the LMM with the defective images along with the text query: *Consider a quality control task in a manufacturing environment. The product shown in the image is defective. Describe the type of defect and its visual characteristics in detail.*

Subsequently, in the second stage we introduce the knowledge acquired in the first stage to the training process of AF-CLIP. To do so, considering the defect-type description of a defective image denoted as dt , we first compute its text embedding. Given the frozen CLIP’s text encoder f_T , its text embedding is computed as: $t^{dt} = f_T(dt)$. Then, considering the set of \mathcal{T}^{dt} of defect-type text embeddings of all the defective images of the auxiliary dataset, we apply k -means clustering in order to obtain the k center embeddings of defect types, $\{\mu_j\}_{j=1}^k$. Next, we introduce the auxiliary subclass objective in the training process of AF-CLIP, both at global and patch levels. Specifically, considering a global defective embedding $\{z_{CLS}^\ell | y=1\}$; note that we use the deepest transformer layer, i.e., $\ell=4$, since it provides the most semantically rich representation, and denote it as z_{CLS}^d for simplicity, and the center embeddings of defect types, $\mu_{j=1}^k$, the additional objective \mathcal{L}_{SAw}^g , is formulated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{SAw}^g = - \frac{z_{CLS}^d \cdot \mu_{j^*}}{\|z_{CLS}^d\| \|\mu_{j^*}\|}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$j^* = \arg \max_{j \in \{1, \dots, k\}} \frac{z_{CLS}^d \cdot \mu_j}{\|z_{CLS}^d\| \|\mu_j\|}. \quad (2)$$

We also apply the above subclass objective to the patch embeddings. More expressly, apart from the global image embeddings of the defective images, we also force the defective patch embeddings $\{z_i^{d, \ell r}, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ across all layers $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and scales $r \in \mathcal{R}$ to come closer to their most similar center embeddings of LMM-generated defect-types, $\mu_{j=1}^k$, which, averaged across layers and scales, leads to the corresponding patch loss \mathcal{L}_{SAw}^p .

The total loss for training the AF-CLIP with the proposed additional objectives, as well as the original AF-CLIP’s training objectives is formulated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_{cls} + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{seg} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{pal} + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{SAw}^g + \lambda_4 \mathcal{L}_{SAw}^p \quad (3)$$

where the parameters $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ and λ_4 control the contribution of the corresponding loss components. The proposed subclass-aware embedding alignment increases cross-category defect discrimination, improving separation between defective and normal samples.

Table 1: Comparison with state-of-the-art methods.

Method	MVTEC		VISA	
	I-AUROC	P-AUROC	I-AUROC	P-AUROC
WinCLIP [8] (CVPR 2023)	91.8	85.1	78.1	79.6
APRIL-GAN [17] (CVPR-W 2023)	86.1	87.6	78.0	94.2
AnomalyCLIP [18] (ICLR 2024)	91.5	91.1	82.1	95.5
AdaCLIP [19] (ECCV 2024)	89.2	88.7	85.8	95.5
SimCLIP [20] (ACMMM 2024)	90.0	91.8	83.1	95.6
AA-CLIP [9] (CVPR 2025)	90.5	91.9	84.6	95.5
Bayes-PFL [21] (CVPR 2025)	92.3	91.8	87.0	95.6
AF-CLIP [10] (ACMMM 2025)	92.3	92.2	87.9	96.1
AF-CLIP + LMM-SAw (Proposed)	93.3	92.4	88.2	96.4

4 Experiments

In this section we present the experimental evaluation of the proposed method, including the description of the used datasets and evaluation metrics, the implementation details, as well as the evaluation results.

4.1 Datasets and Evaluation Metrics

We use two common datasets to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method for industrial ZSAD: MVTEC [23] and VISA [24]. We follow the same experimental setup of the baseline AF-CLIP method. Specifically, we train our model using the VISA dataset and evaluate the zero-shot performance on MVTEC, while for the zero-shot evaluation on VISA, we train our model using MVTEC. As evaluation metric we use the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC). We compute AUROC at both image and pixel levels.

4.2 Implementation Details

Following AF-CLIP, we use the frozen CLIP (ViT-L/14 @336px) model and train the learnable prompts and the additional adapters, using the same values for all the parameters. Specifically, the image size is set to 518, the learnable embedding lengths to 12, the batch size to 8 and the learning rate to $1e-4$, while the parameters λ_1 and λ_2 in eq. (3) are set to 1. The parameter λ_3 of the proposed subclass objective at the global embeddings in eq. (3) is set to 1, while the corresponding parameter λ_4 at the patch embeddings is set to 0.1. The number of cluster centers of the LMM-generated text embeddings is set to 3. The models are trained for 2 epochs. In order to ensure fairness in the comparisons, and since AF-CLIP constitutes our baseline, we reproduce the AF-CLIP experiments using the parameters reported in the original work. All the experiments are conducted utilizing an NVIDIA RTX A4500 with 20GB of GPU memory.

4.3 Experimental Results

In Table 1 we present the evaluation results of the proposed method, denoted as AF-CLIP + LMM-SAw, against AF-CLIP which serves as our baseline. We also include, for completeness, several state-of-the-art CLIP-based methods. Best results are printed in bold. As it is demonstrated, the proposed method considerably improves the state-of-the-art performance at both image and pixel level on both the utilized datasets.

Subsequently, we perform ablation experiments by applying the proposed subclass objective at global-only and patch-only levels. The experimental results are provided in Table 2. We can observe that applying the proposed objective only at global level significantly improves the performance at image level, but it also slightly improves the patch level performance, since it indirectly optimizes the patch embeddings. In addition, applying the proposed objective at patch embeddings only, provides also slight improvements at both image and pixel levels. Evidently, applying the subclass objective at both levels provides considerable improvements at both levels.

Finally, it should be noted that we used the parameters reported in the implementation details section for controlling the contribution of the proposed loss components, as well as for the number of center embeddings k , as they provide consistent performance improvements across both the utilized datasets. However the optimal parameter values may vary for a specific dataset. In Table 3 we provide the experimental results considering the VISA evaluation dataset (MVTEC train) for different values of k and λ_4 . As it is demonstrated, the proposed method provides improvements for various numbers of center embeddings. Finally, it is evident that setting $\lambda_4 = 1$ yields significantly better performance than the default setting, as demonstrated (I-AUROC: 88.9 against 88.2).

Table 2: AUROC results for MVTEC and VISA datasets: applying the proposed objective at global and patch embeddings.

Method	MVTEC		VISA	
	I-AUROC	P-AUROC	I-AUROC	P-AUROC
AF-CLIP (Baseline)	92.3	92.2	87.9	96.1
AF-CLIP + LMM-SAw (global only)	93.0	92.3	88.1	96.2
AF-CLIP + LMM-SAw (patch only)	92.4	92.4	88.1	96.2
AF-CLIP + LMM-SAw (global+patch)	93.3	92.4	88.2	96.4

Table 3: AUROC results for VISA dataset: applying the proposed objectives for different numbers of center embeddings, and values of λ_4 in eq. (3).

k	$\lambda_4 = 0.1$		$\lambda_4 = 1$	
	I-AUROC	P-AUROC	I-AUROC	P-AUROC
0 (Baseline)	87.9	96.1	87.9	96.1
2	88.2	96.4	88.5	96.4
3	88.2	96.4	88.9	96.3
4	88.2	96.4	88.5	96.4
5	88.2	96.4	88.7	96.3

5 Conclusions

In this paper we proposed a novel method for improving the performance of a downstream CLIP-based model for zero-shot industrial anomaly detection. The proposed method consists of two stages. In the first stage, we use an LMM specialized for anomaly detection, in order to extract defect-type descriptions for the defective images of an auxiliary training dataset. In the second stage, we introduce the knowledge extracted in the first stage to the training process of the downstream model for zero-shot anomaly detection. The additional subclass objective maximizes the cosine similarity between the defective image embeddings and their most similar center embedding of the LMM-generated defect-type descriptions. In this way, cross-category defect-type discrimination is achieved, leading to improved defect discrimination, leveraging LMM-produced knowledge. The experimental evaluation, validates the effectiveness of the proposed method.

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